

CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBON FIBERS MODIFIED BY ELECTRODEPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibers were modified by electrodeposition of styrene-co-maleic anhydride (SMA) polymers having different MA content and molecular weight and characterized later by means of ESCA and TGA. ESCA measurement revealed that the electrodeposited fibers have acidic surface layer, with the number of carboxyl groups depending on the MA content of the SMA polymer. TGA results showed that the thickness of the polymer layer is dependent on the deposition time, the current and the copolymers used. Dynamic mechanical analysis of bismaleimide composites reinforced with these fibers gave information about the interaction between the deposited polymer and the matrix polymer.

INTRODUCTION

Electrodeposition of vinyl monomer-co-maleic anhydride polymers onto carbon fibers is one of the techniques to modify the interaction between the fiber and the matrix in polymer composites¹⁻⁸. The electrodeposited polymer layer with finite thickness has its characteristics in chemical composition and morphological feature which will affect directly the stress transferring as well as chemical bridging at the interphasial region in composites. Up to now only a few studies have been performed on the characterization of electrodeposited fibers. The techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, i.e. ESCA) are utilized to investigate coatings of uniform thickness and surface coverage^{1,3,6,8}. However, much information about the treated fibers is desired in order to get insight into the interaction between the deposited polymer and the matrix resin and the interphasial structure in composites.

In the present study, carbon fibers were modified by electrodeposition of styrene-co-maleic anhydride (SMA) polymers having different MA content and molecular weight, using various deposition parameters. The characterization of treated fibers by means of ESCA, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and dynamic mechanical spectroscopy (DMS) showed the chemical composition and geometrical dimensions of electrodeposited SMA layer along with its mechanical behaviour in the composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

PAN-based carbon fibers were purchased from Courtaulds, U.K. in the

form of continuous tows, free of any surface sizings (Hysol Grafil XAS). The diameters of filaments were 6-7 μm . The coating polymers were styrene-co-maleic anhydride polymers with different MA content and molecular weight, which were 28% and 100,000, 39% and 41,000, and 42% and 1,600, respectively. Bismaleimide (BMI) resin was used for fabricating of CF/BMI composite samples.

2. Electrodeposition

Electrodeposition of as-received carbon fibers was conducted continuously on a laboratory set-up. Aqueous solutions of ammonium salts of SMA copolymers (2.5% by weight) were used as the electrodeposition solution, the fiber was electrodeposited as the anode. The parameters varied were electrodeposition time, the current as well as MA content and molecular weight of the copolymers.

3. Characterization

Electrodeposited carbon fibers were analyzed by ESCA directly. The instrument utilized was a Leybold-Heraeus LHS-10 XPS/AES controlled by a Hewlett-Packard HP 1000E Computer System. The ESCA spectra were excited by monochromatized Mg K_{α} radiation, 1253.6 eV. TGA was used to determine the amount of electrodeposited copolymer layer on the carbon fiber surface. The thermal balance was a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 Thermogravimetric System equipped with a First Derivative Computer FDC-1, an Auto-balance AR-2, a Heater Control and a Temperature Program Control UU-1. The powder samples of pure SMA and fiber samples were heated from room temperature to 900°C in N_2 or He atmosphere with the heating rate of 20°C/min. Dynamic mechanical spectra of BMI composite samples reinforced with deposited fibers were measured by means of a torsion pendulum at a frequency of 0.2153 Hz with a heating rate of 20°C/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. ESCA

The concentrations of elements on the electrodeposited fiber surface are shown quantitatively in Table 1, where the detection limit of the concentration is 0.1 at.%. The binding energy $-E_b$ and line-width $-FWHM$ for O(1s), N(1s) and C(1s) are shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Concentrations of elements on electrodeposited carbon fiber surface

Specimen	Polymer	O	N	C	Others
ED211	SMA28,100	12.5	3.9	79.9	3.7
ED441	SMA28,100	9.0	8.3	79.4	3.3
ED423	SMA42,1.6	16.1	3.8	77.2	2.9
ED243	SMA42,1.6	16.0	3.1	78.7	2.2

For fibers of ED423 and ED243, their concentrations of elements of O, N and C are comparative with each other. With fibers of ED211 and ED441, the concentration of oxygen is a little bit lower than that of ED423 and ED243. This does not contradict with the fact that SMA42,1.6 has more carboxyl groups, so a higher concentration of oxygen.

The carbon (1s) peaks in samples of ED211, ED441, ED423 and ED243 are

strongly asymmetrical. The main peak located at 284.6 eV is characteristic of aliphatic, aromatic and graphite carbon. For samples ED423 and ED243, a second peak is present at ca. 288.5 eV, whereas ED211 and ED441 have a shoulder at this position. The peak (shoulder) at 288.5

Table 2 Binding energy -Eb(eV) and line width -FWHM (eV) for O(1s), N(1s) and C(1s)

Specimen	O (1s)		N (1s)		Eb	C (1s)	
	Eb	FWHM	Eb	FWHM		FWHM	
ED211	531.9	2.8	399.9	2.5	284.6 ca. 286.0 288.4 291.9	2.0	
ED441	532.0	2.9	399.4	3.3	284.6 ca. 286.0 288.5 291.6	1.9	
ED423	531.7	2.9	399.7	2.2	284.6 ca. 286.0 288.2 291.4	1.9	
ED243	532.0	2.9	399.9	2.2	284.6 ca. 286.0 288.5 291.5	1.9	

eV is characteristic of carbon triply bonded to oxygen (carboxyl, ester or anhydride groups). This peak is larger for ED423 and ED243, in accordance with the fact that the MA-styrene ratio in SMA42,1.6 is higher than that in SMA28,100. The shoulder at 286.0 eV is characteristic of carbon singly bonded to oxygen (ether, ester, alcohol and etc.). The shoulder at ca. 291.6 eV indicates the presence of a conjugated carbon system, which exists in one of the monomer, styrene. It should be noted that parts of the carbon fiber surface are possibly visible, because the shape of C (1s) signals looks rather like that of the unsized carbon fiber XAS than that of the pure SMA28,100 copolymer.

For all of these samples the O (1s) peaks are asymmetrical and broad, which indicates several types of oxygen present on the sample surface. It is shown by a detailed investigation that nitrogen signals come from PAN-based carbon fiber surface and/or the deposited layer, onto which NH_4^+ ions from the electrodeposition solution may attach.

It can be concluded that the carbon fibers electrodeposited with SMA copolymer layers have an acidic surface, where the amount of the carboxyl groups is proportional to the maleic anhydride content in pristine bulk polymers. With the help of ESCA the elemental composition and the possible contamination of the fiber surface can be detected.

2. TGA

In Table 3, the weight losses of the SMA copolymers and carbon fibers

with deposited SMA are listed. The data can be classified into three groups: varying the deposition current, the deposition time and the copolymer one at a time, while maintaining the other parameters constant, for sake of convenient comparison.

Table 3 The weight loss of bulk polymer and deposited polymer on carbon fiber surface

Specimen	Time	Current	Polymer	Weight loss, %			
				900°C	800°C	700°C	600°C
			SMA28,100	98.2	97.5	97.4	97.1
			SMA42,1.6	98.0	96.5	96.0	95.6
ED411	4	1	SMA28,100	7.3	5.8	4.3	3.5
ED421	4	2	SMA28,100	5.2	4.5	4.0	3.3
ED441	4	4	SMA28,100	5.6	3.3	2.0	0.9
ED423	4	2	SMA42,1.6	6.0	3.8	2.5	1.4
ED211	2	1	SMA28,100	2.8	2.0	1.3	0.5
ED221	2	2	SMA28,100	2.0	1.5	1.0	0.5
ED222	2	2	SMA39,41	2.0	1.4	0.8	0.3
ED223	2	2	SMA42,1.6	5.0	3.6	2.3	0.9
ED241	2	4	SMA28,100	2.3	1.6	1.0	0.3
ED242	2	4	SMA39,41	2.3	1.7	1.3	0.5
ED243	2	4	SMA42,1.6	3.7	3.0	2.1	1.0
ED111	1	1	SMA28,100	2.4	1.9	1.5	1.0
ED121	1	2	SMA28,100	4.3	3.4	2.4	1.0
ED122	1	2	SMA39,41	2.6	2.0	1.4	0.7
ED141	1	4	SMA28,100		3.7	2.9	2.0
ED142	1	4	SMA39,41	5.4	3.7	2.7	1.7

It seems that in the range of the current, the time and the polymer chosen for the present investigation, the amount of the deposited polymer decreases with increasing current at constant time when the time is longer for SMA42,1.6 (compare ED223 to ED243). The basic cause of this trend can be traced to the evolution of oxygen at the anode⁶. For SMA28,100 and SMA39,41, at a medium time, current level 2 and 4 (ED221, 222; ED241, 242) make no difference in the deposit amount of the polymer layer. When the time is shorter (level 1) higher current leads to more deposit (ED111 to ED121; ED122 to ED142).

As for the influence of the time, at the current level 1, the amount of the deposits increases with increasing time (ED111, 211 and 411). At the current level 2, the medium time deposits SMA28,100 and SMA39,41 the least amount (ED221,222), while the long time causes the largest one (ED421). At the current level 4, the medium time causes the least deposit of SMA28,100 (ED241); the shorter time deposits much more polymers of SMA28,100 and SMA39,41 on the fiber surface (ED141,142). In the practical consideration, the excessive deposit would hold the fiber together, making separation difficult without breaking the fibers.

The amount of deposited polymer is dependent on the polymer. At the time level 2 and current level 2, SMA28,100 and SMA39,41 have less weight loss (ED221,222), while SMA42,1.6 has more deposit (ED223). At medium time and large current, SMA28,100 and SMA39,41 have comparable amounts of weight loss (ED241,242). The higher the MA content and the lower the molecular weight, the larger the amount of deposited polymer is. This trend might be attributed to the migration rate which is

proportional to the electrical force acting on the polymer anions and proportional inversely to the mass of polymer of equivalent weight deposited by unit charge⁶.

Principally speaking, longer time leads to more deposits than shorter one does; larger current leads to less deposits than smaller one does. However, these situations will occur in their certain range and combination, so that other relationships may be found by other researchers. In the range of these parameters chosen in the present study, the competing process of electrodeposition parameters just appear, which is useful to understanding of the complexity of the electrodeposition process.

The thickness of deposited polymer layer on fiber surface can be estimated from an expression, assuming this layer has a uniform thickness:

$$t = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(d^2 \cdot \frac{\rho_1 W_2}{\rho_2 W_1} + d^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - d \right]$$

where, t is the thickness of polymer layer, d is the diameter of the fiber, ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the density of carbon fiber and the polymer, respectively, W_1 and W_2 are the respective weight fraction of fibers and the polymer. If the following data are adopted for calculation of the thickness of polymer layer deposited on carbon fiber surface: $\rho_1 = 1.81 \text{ g/mm}^2$, $\rho = 1.2 \text{ g/mm}^2$ and $d = 6.9 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, then the thickness vs. the weight loss measured by TGA can be listed in Table 4.

Table 4 The thickness of deposited layers

Weight loss of polymer, %	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0
Thickness of polymer, nm	13	26	53	80	107	134	162	190

In this calculation, some remarks should be made about the polymer density, ρ_2 . It was found that the deposited SMA layer in the vicinity of carbon fiber surface became insoluble in acetone, despite the bulk polymer was soluble in this solvent³. This fact indicates the possible increase of the packing density of SMA copolymer in the inner deposited layer.

The authors would like to point out that several researchers^{1,3} got different results for improving the adhesion between carbon fiber and epoxy resin with the same electrodeposition technique. This seems to show that the thickness of deposited polymer layer is one of critical conditions, in addition to the compatibility between the deposited polymer and the resin used as the matrix.

3. DMS

Fig.1 shows the dynamic mechanical spectra of BMI composite samples reinforced by Hysol EXAS, an epoxy-sized carbon fiber, (A) and ED223 (B). The values of shear storage modulus, G' , of the sample A are a little higher than those of the sample B at lower temperature, while the latter is higher than the former at the temperature above 260°C. The spectra of tangent of loss angle, $\tan \delta$, of both samples have a similar shape except the sample B has a larger and broader loss peak at 250°C. These data mean that the SMA interphase layer in carbon fiber/BMI composite does not decrease the shear modulus of the compos-

ite and does not impair the heat resistance of the composite, although SMA42,1.6 itself is brittle and has a rather low glass transition

Fig. 1 Dynamic mechanical spectra of BMI composite samples reinforced by Hysol EXAS (o) and ED223 (●).

temperature. The possible chemical reaction between SMA copolymer and BMI resin contributes to good dynamical mechanical properties of CF/SMA/BMI composite. So it is reasonable that the introduction of a polymer interlayer between the carbon fiber and the polymer matrix can lead to improvements of interlaminar shear strength, flexural strength, impact strength, thermal endurance and hydrothermal endurance to more or less extent at the same time⁵.

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